

Pyridoyl Dipeptides and their Derivatives as Possible Tuberculostats. Part II: Nicotinoyl Derivatives

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Nicotinoylglycylglycine, nicotinoyl glycyl-DL-methionine and a number of their derivatives have been synthesised and tested for their *in vitro* antitubercular activity. Out of the 26 compounds tested, two compounds partially inhibited the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv at 1:10,000 dilution.

In a quest for new antitubercular agents, a few amino acid conjugates of pyridine carboxylic acids,¹ pyridine acrylic acids² and chlorophenoxyacetic acids³, some N-acetyl-dipeptide derivatives⁴ and some peptide conjugates of nicotinic acid⁵ have been prepared and tested. In further pursuit of this quest, nicotinoylglycylglycine ethyl ester, nicotinoylglycyl-DL-methionine ethyl ester, their corresponding acids, hydrazides and a few hydrazones derivatives have now been synthesised and screened.

Nicotinoylglycine could be prepared in good yield, only by condensing the nicotinic acid azide with glycine.⁶ This was further condensed with glycine and DL-methionine ethyl esters using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCCI) as the peptide bond forming reagent⁷ to obtain the corresponding N-nicotinoyl dipeptide esters. The condensation was carried out in dimethyl formamide (DMF) at low temperatures (0 to -5°). The N-nicotinoyl dipeptide esters were hydrolysed to the corresponding N-nicotinoyl dipeptides and also converted to the hydrazides which with different aldehydes gave 1,2-disubstituted hydrazine derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL**

Nicotinoylglycylglycine ethyl ester(I).—Nicotinoylglycine⁸ (1.80 g.) dissolved in dry DMF (30 ml.) was added under constant stirring to glycine ethyl ester (1.03 g.) and DCCI (2.06 g.) in DMF (20 ml.) while cooling the flask in freezing mixture. The reaction mixture was kept at 0 to -5° for 48 hr. and the unreacted DCCI was decomposed with a few drops of glacial acetic acid. Dicyclohexylurea was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to

*Pharmacological screening was carried out by Professor M. Sirsi, Pharmacology Laboratory of this Institute.

**All melting points are uncorrected.

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dryness. The residue was taken in ethylacetate and the insoluble portion filtered. The filtrate was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate, concentrated and light petroleum (b. p. 40-60°) added; the product obtained was recrystallised from ethylacetate—light petroleum and had m. p. 143-44°; yield; 1.63 g. (61.3%). Reported⁸, m. p. 144-45°.

Nicotinoylglycylglycine (II).—This was prepared from (I) following the method of Meyer and Graf⁸. The ethyl ester (I) was treated with equimolecular amount of KOH, the potassium salt converted to the insoluble silver salt and then decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid whereby the insoluble silver chloride could be filtered and the product obtained from the filtrate after concentrating and cooling.

Nicotinoylglycylglycylid hydrazide (III).—The ester (I) (2.65 g.) was refluxed in ethanol (50 ml.) with excess of 80% hydrazine hydrate (2 g.) for 4-6 hr. Ethanol and excess of hydrazine hydrate were removed under suction and the residue was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, and had m. p. 221°; yield, 1.91 g. (76%). (Found: C, 48.04; H, 5.24; N, 27.48; $C_{10}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires C, 47.82; H, 5.18; N, 27.80%). I. R.: 3436 cm^{-1} (NH stretching), 1650 cm^{-1} (amide I band), 1550 cm^{-1} (amide II band).

Condensation of aldehydes with III: Formation of 1,2-disubstituted hydrazine derivatives (IV—XIII, Table I): General procedure:—Equimolecular quantities of the hydrazide (III) and the aldehyde were refluxed in absolute ethanol for 6-12 hr. On being concentrated and cooled, the product crystallised out which was further recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

Nicotinoylglycyl-DL-methionine ethyl ester (XIV).—Nicotinoylglycine (1.80 g.) dissolved in dry DMF (30 ml.) was added to DL-methionine ethyl ester (1.77 g.) and DCCI (2.06 g.) in DMF (20 ml.) at 0 to -5°. The product was isolated as in the case of (I), and had m. p. 103°; yield, 2.22 g. (65.48%). (Found: C, 53.17; H, 6.30; N, 11.95; $C_{13}H_{21}O_4N_2S$ requires C, 53.07; H, 6.34; N, 12.38%). I. R.: 3378 cm^{-1} (NH stretching), 1739 cm^{-1} (ester C=O), 1653 cm^{-1} (amide I band), 1543 cm^{-1} (amide II band).

Nicotinoylglycyl-DL-methionine (XV).—The ester (XIV) (2 g.) was stirred with 10% excess of 1N potassium hydroxide solution (6.50 ml.) for 6 hr. The unreacted ester was filtered and the filtrate acidified with 1N hydrochloric acid to pH 3.5. The solution on keeping in the refrigerator for several hours, gave a product which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol and had m. p. 252°; yield, 0.62 g. (33.0%). (Found: N, 14.06; $C_{13}H_{21}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 13.56%), I. R.: 3446 cm^{-1} (NH stretching), 1724 cm^{-1} (acid C=O), 1661 cm^{-1} (amide I band), 1541 cm^{-1} (amide II band).

Nicotinoylglycyl-DL-methionine hydrazide (XVI).—The ester (XIV) (7.5 g.) in ethanol (75 ml.) was refluxed with excess of 80% hydrazine hydrate (4.5 g.) for 4 hr; excess of ethanol and hydrazine hydrate were removed under suction and the residue was crystallised from ethanol, and had m. p. 184°; yield, 5.30 g. (73.70%). (Found: C, 47.52; H, 5.93; N, 21.18. $C_{12}H_{19}O_3N_2S$ requires C, 47.99; H, 5.85; N, 21.18%). I. R.: 3413 cm^{-1} (NH stretching), 1642 cm^{-1} (amide I band), 1543 cm^{-1} (amide II band).

Condensation of aldehydes with XVI: formation of 1,2 disubstituted hydrazine derivatives (XVII—XXVI, Table 1): General procedure:—Equimolecular quantities of (XVI)

and the aldehyde were refluxed in anhydrous ethanol for 6-12 hr. The product was crystallised out on concentrating and cooling and was further recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

TABLE I
1,2-Disubstituted hydrazine derivatives

R ₂ = aldehyde residue	Compd No.	m.p. °C	Formula	%Nitrogen	
				Found.	Calcd.
R ₁ =H					
-(3,4-O-CH ₂ -O)C ₆ H ₃	IV	246	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₅	18.01	18.27
2-C ₆ H ₇ N	V	234	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆	21.90	21.54
4-(CH ₃) ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	VI	250	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆	22.13	21.97
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	VII	239	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₅	19.32	19.17
2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	VIII	219-221	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₅	19.85	19.72
3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	IX	225-226	"	19.23	19.72
4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	X	258	"	19.62	19.72
4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	XI	219	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅	19.51	18.96
3-C ₂ H ₅ N	XII	252	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆	24.36	24.68
4-C ₂ H ₅ N	XIII	217	"	24.29	24.68
R ₁ =CH ₂ CH ₂ SCH ₃					
-(3,4-O-CH ₂ -O)C ₆ H ₃	XVII	231	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₅ S	15.15	15.31
2-C ₆ H ₇ N	XVIII	130	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	17.63	18.09
4-(CH ₃) ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄	XIX	167	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	18.30	18.42
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	XX	182	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₆ S	15.61	15.93
2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	XXI	198	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₆ S	15.91	16.30
3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	XXII	206-8	"	15.90	16.30
4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	XXIII	173	"	15.81	16.30
4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	XXIV	201	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₆ S	15.70	15.80
3-C ₂ H ₅ N	XXV	169	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₆ S	20.73	20.28
4-C ₂ H ₅ N	XXVI	113	"	20.37	20.28

The antitubercular activity of these compounds were determined as reported in the earlier publication.¹ Out of the 26 compounds prepared and tested, 1-[N(nicotinoyl) glycyglycyl]-2-p-methoxybenzylidene hydrazine and 1-[N(nicotinoyl) glycy]-DL-methionyl]-2-nicotinylidene hydrazine partially inhibited the growth of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv at 1:10,000 dilution. Rest of the compounds were inactive.

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